

NEUROLOGICAL DISEASES - AS A SOCIAL AND HYGIENIC PROBLEM

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Abstract. *Neurological diseases are pathologies of the organs of the central and peripheral nervous system. They are often the cause of disability and death of the population. Neurology combines various directions for the study of normal and pathological conditions of the nervous system, it analyzes the mechanisms of occurrence, causes, symptoms, methods of therapy, preventive measures. The diagnosis and treatment of patients with neurological diseases occupies the main role of medicine.*

Key words: *migraine, epilepsy, social problem, neurological disorders.*

НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ БОЛЕЗНИ - КАК СОЦИАЛЬНО-ГИГИЕНИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА

Аннотация. *Неврологические заболевания – это патологии органов центральной и периферической нервной системы. Они часто являются причиной инвалидности и гибели населения. Неврология объединяет различные направления изучения нормальных и патологических состояний нервной системы, анализирует механизмы возникновения, причины, симптомы, методы терапии, меры профилактики. Диагностика и лечение больных с неврологическими заболеваниями занимает основную роль медицины.*

Ключевые слова: *мигрень, эпилепсия, социальная проблема, неврологические расстройства.*

INTRODUCTION

Neurology is a science that studies the normal state of the nervous system and treats various pathologies that have arisen as a result of external factors and diseases of other organs. Neurological problems are usually divided into two fundamental blocks: pyramidal and extrapyramidal. The extrapyramidal system is a structure of the brain that is responsible for balance, emotions, posture, movement and muscle tension. Failures in the operation of this system lead to the development of hypokinesia or hyperkinesia. Hyperkinesia is a pathological condition in which there is an overestimated number of involuntary movements. This happens when neurons are affected. The disease can spread to all human organs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The disease has no age restrictions. Hypokinesia – gives the opposite effect, as a result of which motor activity becomes inhibited. Develops against the background of an inactive lifestyle and psychological disorders. The pyramidal system is responsible for coordination and reflexes. In case of system failures, the integrity of the cortical-muscular pathway is violated. There are many types of diseases with their outcomes. Infectious neurological diseases – develop against the background of pathogenic influence of viruses, bacteria, fungi, worm infestations. Symptoms are associated with damage to the central nervous system (brain and spinal cord). Typical examples: encephalitis, meningitis, malaria. Gene and chromosomal pathologies are the result of damage to genetic material caused by mutations of individual genes (amino acid, lipid metabolism diseases)

or chromosomal abnormalities (Down syndrome, Edwards syndrome). Hereditary predisposition is characteristic of epilepsy, Alzheimer's disease, multiple sclerosis. Traumatic neurological disorders are associated with damage to the central or peripheral parts. Typical examples: concussion of the brain, spinal cord injury, compression of the sciatic nerve (sciatica). Tumor diseases of the central nervous system are a special case of traumatic pathologies. Benign or malignant structures, when overgrown, put pressure on nerve tissues, causing damage to them. Vascular neurological pathologies are associated with impaired blood supply and nutrition of nervous structures, mainly the brain. Over time, they can cause strokes and paralysis. Problems of the autonomic system: Raynaud's disease, mountain sickness, migraine, vegetative-vascular dystonia, Parkinson's disease, cerebral palsy, enuresis, muscular rheumatism, increased sweating, Alzheimer's disease. In addition, with lesions of various nervous structures of the brain, specific neurological symptoms occur.

RESULTS

The main examples of damage to the central nervous system: damage to the cerebral cortex of the large hemispheres: hearing, speech, memory problems, constant or periodic headache, confusion, frequent fainting; injuries to subcortical structures: failures or complete shutdown of visual function, intolerance to bright light, slowing reaction speed; disruption of the Varoliev bridge: difficulties with concentration, inability to concentrate, problems with coordination of movements; damage to cerebellar structures: problems with coordination, paresis, paralysis; abnormalities in the structure of the medulla oblongata: respiratory function disorders, tissue hypoxia, problems with coordination of movements. The spinal part of the central nervous system is responsible for conducting impulses from the brain to organs and tissues, responsible for the motor and sensory functions of the body. The defeat of the nervous system entails the defeat of other organs and leads to inactivity.

DISCUSSION

There are many reasons that cause headaches. Migraine is manifested by headaches on the one hand, ending with vomiting, bringing relief. Before a migraine attack, aura – visual phenomena (visual disturbances, flickering, lightning), unpleasant sensations (photophobia, increased sensitivity of odors) may occur. Then comes an attack of severe headache, which does not allow you to work or rest normally. Analgesics do not help with such a picture. It is necessary to take special medications. In addition to migraines, there is a tension headache that occurs due to the constant tension of the muscles of the scalp of the skull. Vascular headache occurs against the background of a spasm of the cerebral vessels, an increase in blood pressure. With a brain tumor, a headache occurs caused by compression of blood vessels or cerebrospinal fluid disorders.

CONCLUSIONS

The improvements in public health achieved through effective treatment of headaches are significant and do not depend on the reimbursement of indirect costs associated with these disorders. Treatment of neurological diseases requires accurate timely diagnosis and consistent therapy. Failure to comply with medical recommendations, inconsistency of treatment and attempts to solve the problem independently can result in an unfavorable outcome and cause severe disability and even death. Neurological and mental disorders significantly affect the severity of the disease and, in the absence of timely diagnosis and adequate therapy, significantly worsen the prognosis and increase the risk of death. The recommendations proposed by an international group of experts on the classification, diagnosis and therapy of neurological disorders will allow all

specialists facing this severe manifestation of diseases to diagnose and prescribe adequate therapy in a timely manner, which will help avoid the progression of the lesion, improve the quality of life of patients and the prognosis. Further study of diseases will provide a better understanding of their relationship with other diseases for the prevention of consequences and will contribute to the inclusion of such disorders in classification criteria and recommendations for the management of patients with neurological disorders.

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